

The background of the cover is a close-up photograph of two hands, palms up, holding a small, yellow, textured world map. The hands are positioned in the center of the frame, with the fingers slightly curled around the edges of the map. The map is a simple outline of the world's continents, colored in a bright yellow. The background behind the hands is a dark, out-of-focus blue.

EABIS ANNUAL REPORT 2010-2011

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Foreword

Dear Members, Aspiring Members & Friends,

It is our pleasure to share the latest Annual Report with you on the eve of EABIS' ten year anniversary, which we formally celebrate in Lausanne, Switzerland. It is remarkable to think that a decade has passed since the first Colloquium took place at INSEAD. In early July, over 300 people will gather at various events hosted by IMD (Colloquium), Ecole Hôtelière (PhD Conference) and the European University's Château Maison Blanche (Decennial Event). These will offer us valuable time to review the progress made in our first decade, to renew our shared commitment to the unique collaborative model underpinning The Academy, and to anticipate some of the major opportunities and challenges which lie ahead.

In last year's report, we highlighted three major trends that were shaping – and which continue to shape – the strategic development of EABIS:

1. **Geographic Expansion**
2. **Thematic Expansion**
3. **Capability Enhancement**

This year's report underlines the positive trajectory which The Academy is following. In 2011 we appointed new Directors for Asia and the Americas, while adding members from countries as diverse as India, Morocco, Fiji, Brazil and Finland. By end 2011, agreements had been signed to establish EABIS offices in New York and Shanghai. In that same

period, we staged our first conferences in South Asia, the Middle East and the United States, while events are already being planned for Thailand, Australia, southern Africa, the US and China in 2012 and the start of 2013.

In parallel with the geographic growth, EABIS' portfolio is evolving to engage with more areas of mainstream practice, research and teaching around sustainability-related issues. The **Advancing Health Decision Making** platform – designed and run with Johnson & Johnson and Rutgers University – has brought together global experts throughout 2011 to reflect on new ways to improve the quality of health outcomes for public, private and civil society actors. The **Practical Wisdom for Management** project, co-led by Yale University and with the active support of EFMD, has harnessed thought leadership from the Christian, Chinese, Hebrew, Islamic and Indian traditions to broaden our understanding of responsible management in the 21st century.

Two other prime examples of the network's move into the mainstream of sustainability are our past two Annual Colloquia: CR and Emerging Markets in St. Petersburg (2010) and an outstanding follow-up on the role of business in development and developing markets, hosted by INSEAD in October. Building on the insights and debate which took place in Fontainebleau, the EABIS

network will this autumn construct an international research group to bid for € 2.5 million in European Union funding on this precise theme. Similar exercises are anticipated on the themes of social entrepreneurship and sustainable lifestyles.

Heading into The Academy's second decade, though, we know that we cannot rest on our laurels. Our Decennial Conference in January 2012 reinforced the calls for transformative, systems-level adaptation within companies and also within the global management education sector. In acknowledging the scale and complexity of the challenges ahead, and the difficulty of achieving deep and lasting change, it is clear that our network must embrace innovative thinking, practice, knowledge development and training approaches to remain at the forefront of our field. In this regard, our 2012 Colloquium at IMD gives us the perfect launching pad, as we explore the key dimensions of **strategic innovation for sustainability**.

We look forward very much to working with you all to deliver daily value and to ensure that EABIS launches its second decade in the strongest possible position. In the months to come, we will actively involve you all in delivering **EABIS 2.0** – a global platform of excellence for the next ten years and beyond!

Prof. Gilbert Lenssen
President

Simon Pickard
Director General

Prof. Mollie Painter-Morland
Academic Director

John Swannick
Executive Director

01

Delivering Value

Headlines 2010-2011

In line with the original “Raising the Bar” mandate, and subsequent internationalisation strategy, EABIS has steadily increased its level of activity, membership diversity and intellectual scope in the past two years.

More than 40 events coordinated or co-sponsored
11 publications
29 new partners, members and affiliated networks recruited
€ 850k approx. Secured for corporate projects and strategic programmes
€ 100k approx. secured in in-kind resources from Corporate sponsors
\$150k approx. secured from US Foundations to support North American expansion
1st conference delivered in partnership with the European Commission (Brussels, Apr 2010)
1st event in China (CEIBS Shanghai, Jun 2010)
1st Colloquium staged outside of western Europe (St. Petersburg, Sept 2010)
1st event in US (Rutgers and Johnson&Johnson HQ, May 2011)
1st event in the Middle East (Ben-Gurion University of Negev, July 2011)
1st event in Africa (Al-Akawayn University, November 2011)
Direct contributions to new EU policy frameworks (FP7)

Framework for Delivery

Since its original “Raising The Bar” Strategy was launched in 2006, the EABIS Central Team has worked to an evolving mandate focused on:

Membership focus and delivery

Membership Internationalisation

Membership Responsiveness, Inclusiveness & Delivery through:

- Governance
- Communication
- Accessible Resources
- Publications and Outputs

Resources

Renew existing financial resources and funding

Expand financial resources and funding expand

Human and knowledge capital resources

Channel resources to achieve mission and benefit members

Key stakeholders and external environment

Provide Institutional support to EU Agenda

Promote collaborative development of UN PRME

Develop strategic international partnerships

Managing Strategic Implementation

Measure and Manage Performance

Monitor Threats and Challenges

Implement Emergent and Adaptive Strategy

Programme and Activities

An overarching Business in Society Framework

- Dialogue and Debate
- Knowledge development and Research
- Learning and Education
- Outreach

Expand and explore new programme areas of high relevance

Improve operations and membership service

Events 2010

APR

International Webinar: Assessing and Measuring CR Impacts at Micro and Macro Levels, EABIS, Brussels
Future of Economics and Management Symposium Università Cattolica & ISTUD, Stresa

MAY

4th Annual EABIS Leaders Forum: Sustainable Performance in a Changing Business Environment. GDF Suez, Brussels

JUN

GOLDEN[™] Project Conference: Building Dynamic Capabilities for Sustainability, SDA Bocconi, Milan
UN PRME 2nd Global Forum for Responsible Management Education Fordham University, New York
Practical Wisdom for Management Symposium: The Chinese Classical Traditions, CEIBS, Shanghai

JUL

International Webinar: Managing and Measuring CR Performance, EABIS, Brussels
Mainstreaming CR in Executive Education Conference, ISTUD, Stresa

SEPT

EABIS 8th Annual PhD Conference , St. Petersburg GSOM, St. Petersburg
EABIS 9th Annual Colloquium: CR & Emerging Markets, St. Petersburg GSOM ,St. Petersburg
International Webinar: Delivering CR through Effective Change Management, EABIS, Brussels

OCT

Enhancing Business/Government Dialogue: Policy Round Table, EPPA, Brussels
Enhancing Business/Government Dialogue: Corporate Round Table, EPPA, Brussels

NOV

5th EU Multi-Stakeholder Forum on CSR, European Commission, Brussels
1st EABIS Experiential Learning Congress, ESMT, Berlin
2nd Peter Drucker Forum: Shaping the Future of Management, Drucker Society of Austria, Vienna

DEC

10th European Corporate Governance Conference, EU Presidency, Brussels

Events 2011

FEB

IMPACT Project, Policy and Stakeholder Round Table, EABIS, Brussels
Microsoft Enabling Technologies for a Low Carbon Economy Round Table, Microsoft, Brussels
International Webinar – Trends in Non-Financial Disclosure, EABIS, Brussels
Webinar: Enabling technologies for health - Gaining Traction on European Health Systems

APR

Innovation and Sustainability Symposium, ESC Burgundy, Dijon
Ethics and HR Research Symposium, Monash / RHUL, London
CR & Reputation Symposium, Belgacom, Brussels

MAY

Responsible Business Summit: Entrepreneurship Session, Ethical Corp, London
Advancing Global Health Decision-Making Launch Conference, Rutgers, New Brunswick

JUN

PRME 2011 Global Forum, EFMD, Brussels
6th EABIS Annual Leaders Forum: Consumer Perceptions of Corporate Responsibility and the Implications for Business Reputation and Brands, EABIS, Brussels

JUL

Practical Wisdom Conference – Jewish Traditions, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, EABIS, Yale and EFMD, Jerusalem

SEP

IABS Annual Conference, HUB, Brussels
Governmentality and Corporate Responsibility Symposium, Royal Holloway University of London, London

OCT

Deans Forum: The Next Decade of EABIS, INSEAD, Fontainebleau
General Assembly, INSEAD, Fontainebleau
10th Annual Colloquium: CR and Development, INSEAD, Fontainebleau
9th Annual PhD Conference, CEDEP, Fontainebleau
2nd Advancing Global Health Decision-Making Conference, CEDEP, Fontainebleau

NOV

IMPACT Project Stakeholder Round Table, EABIS, Brussels
Practical Wisdom for Management from the Islamic Tradition, Yale, EABIS, EFMD, Al Akhawayn University, Morocco
3rd Peter Drucker Forum: Shaping the Future of Management, Drucker Society of Austria, Vienna

Projects 2010-2011

Projects within 5 thematic domains:

**ETHICS & LEADERSHIP
SUSTAINABILITY
GOVERNANCE
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT**

**EDUCATION &
LEARNING**

Projects 2010-2011

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Chinese Classical Traditions

Chinese Traditions – CEIBS Shanghai, Yale, EABIS, EFMD

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Jewish Traditions

Jewish Traditions – Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Yale, EABIS, EFMD

Practical Wisdom for Management from Islamic Traditions

Islamic Traditions – Al-Akhawayn University, Yale, EABIS, EFMD

CR, Ethics and HRM

Monash, Royal Holloway

Enabling Technologies for a Low Carbon Economy

Microsoft, EABIS

Advancing Global Health Decision Making

Johnson & Johnson, Rutgers University, EABIS

GOLDEN Project: Building Dynamic Capabilities for Sustainability

Bocconi University, INSEAD, EABIS, Microsoft, Telecom Italia, ENI, ESADE, Bath, IESE, Griffith, Aarhus

Mainstreaming Sustainability in Asset Management & Equity Research

Dexia, EABIS

Stakeholder Media

INSEAD, RSM Erasmus, Rutgers

Innovation for Sustainability: A PhD Training Network Proposal to the EU

EABIS, Copenhagen, Exeter, Leuphana, Manchester, Nyenrode, RSM Erasmus, Vlerick, University of Cape Town

Projects 2010-2011

Organisational Change and Institutional Governance in Healthcare

Kingston, Royal Holloway, Copenhagen, Manchester, SDA Bocconi

Implementing Environmental & Social Policies in Supply Chains

Bath University, Catholic University of Milan, KU Eichstaett-Ingolstadt

Corporate Governance

Belgian Institute of Directors (GUBERNA), Vlerick, Cranfield, EABIS

Transforming Business-Government Relations for the 21st Century

EPPA, Cranfield, EABIS

Governmentality and Corporate Responsibility

Royal Holloway, ESADE, Amsterdam, Copenhagen

“IMPACT” Project

Oeko Institute, EABIS, Aalto, CEU, Copenhagen, IESE, INSEAD, Leon Kozminski, MIP Milan, Nottingham, TiasNimbas, Vlerick

The Future of Economics and Management

Catholic University of Milan, Bocconi University, INSEAD, EABIS

Valuing Non-Financial Performance: An Enterprise 2020 Collaborative Project

Lloyds Banking Group, Solvay, Telecom Italia, CSR Europe, EABIS

Corporate Responsibility and the Social Value of Brands

Unilever, Bath University, Royal Holloway, INSEAD

Consumer Perceptions of Corporate Responsibility

INSEAD, Durham Business School

Corporate Responsibility and Reputation

Ketchum Pleon, Belgacom, EABIS

Assessing the Impact of UN Global Compact LEAD initiative: Development Phase

EABIS, Ashridge, UN Global Compact, UN PRME

Projects 2010-2011

1st Experiential Learning Congress
EABIS, Agentur Mehrwert and ESMT Berlin
**Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility in
Executive Education**
Fondazione ISTUD, Ashridge, IMD
Innovative Pedagogies for Sustainability
Copenhagen, Nottingham, EABIS
**Case Studies on Integrating Corporate
Responsibility in the CEE Region**
Leon Kozminski, CEU, St. Petersburg GSOM, CSR
Ukraine

Publications 2010-2011

Valuing Non-Financial Performance: A European Framework for Company and Investor Dialogue

This report is the final outcome of the European Laboratory on Valuing Non-Financial Performance – facilitated by CSR Europe and EABIS and led by Lloyds Banking Group and Telecom Italia. It proposes an evidence-based and -tested framework of principles and common indicators that can be used to enhance relations between companies and investors.

It also seeks to create a compelling case for the inclusion of NFP in their dialogue as a platform for more productive debate on the value of corporate responsibility. The Laboratory was supported throughout by the “Sustainable Value” research – see opposite

Special Issue of the Journal of Management Development 2010: Practical Wisdom in Management from the Christian Traditions

This Special Issue is the first of seven journals and six books to be generated by the EABIS-Yale-EFMD “Practical Wisdom” Project – a global innovation in management knowledge development and dialogue. It provides an interdisciplinary exploration of the virtue of practical wisdom within the (Catholic and Protestant)

Christian traditions in relationship to business and business education. As such, it is the first of several steps towards defining an integral rationality that helps students of management to see their path as a profession, as well as the benefits of being wise and not merely smart.

Special Issue of the Journal of Management Development 2011: Practical Wisdom for Management from the Chinese Classical Traditions

Chinese culture increasingly will permeate international culture and move from peripheral to mainstream status. To ignore this in management education would be a grave oversight.

The issue offers insights into the value of practical wisdom from Confucianism, the origins of Chinese classical traditions and Daoism, and the various streams of thought within the classical Chinese traditions and their contemporary relevance.

Special Issue of the Journal of Management Development 2011 - Introduction to the Special Issue: Integrating Sustainability in Business Models

The purpose of this journal is to showcase a range of strategic change case studies, conceptualized and realized by a group of scholars engaged in the Global Organizational Learning and Development Network (GOLDEN) for Sustainability programme.

The cases offer good illustrations of the ongoing transition by both medium-sized and multinational corporations dealing with learning and change challenges posed by the identification and management of sustainability issues. The selected cases represent firms operating in diverse contexts and industries, and are developed by scholars specializing in various fields connected to corporate responsibility and sustainability.

Publications 2010-2011

From Faith to Faith-Consistent Investing: Religious Institutions and Their Investment Practices (ESADE, Vlerick, 3iG)

This report is the outcome of a groundbreaking study conducted by ESADE, Vlerick Leuven Ghent and 3iG Investment Group to examine whether or not faith institutions' beliefs are reflected in their financial investment practices, as well as how they manage that process.

Given the growing interest in responsible investment and the fact that faith investors are possibly the third largest group of investors in the world, the report sheds light on a new research field of major importance.

EABIS Corporate Responsibility in Executive Education Mapping 2010

The EABIS CR in Executive Education Mapping was published in June 2010 to coincide with the Executive Education seminar hosted at Fondazione ISTUD in Stresa, Italy, supported by EABIS' Corporate Founding Partners. This report reveals that while a few centres of excellence are undoubtedly flourishing and

expanding thanks to a substantial demand from global brand clients, there is still a notable gap between supply and demand in CR and sustainability content. Nonetheless, recent announcements of new and relevant courses indicate some progress is being made. Our second mapping in 2012 will surely reveal more about its scope and scale.

EABIS Research 2002-2010: Business in Society and Corporate Responsibility

Building upon the work of the talented scholars within our network, this report highlights the diversity of themes being addressed by our member institutions. This overview serves also to underline the deep and unwavering commitment of EABIS to cutting-edge knowledge development and learning.

With its unique collaborative model of business – academic partnership, EABIS members and its secretariat have contributed more than 100 internal and external outputs from research. These include peer-reviewed journals, papers, cases, and other published articles, as well as the growing series of EABIS branded books.

Towards Greater Corporate Responsibility: Conclusions from FP6 Research on CSR (European Commission)

This publication was launched by DG Research at the April 2010 conference on the future of CR research. It examines the results of four CR-focused projects implemented under the EU's 6th Framework – including CSR PLATFORM and RESPONSE, led by EABIS and INSEAD. It also seeks to draw a broader picture of corporate responsibility in the EU policy domain,

and how European research has contributed to advances in knowledge and learning. It closes with an overview of key insights and priority areas for business in society research, many of which were identified by EABIS and its members.

Publications 2010-2011

Special Issue of the Corporate Governance Journal 2010: The Future of Corporate Governance

This Special Issue is produced by EABIS together with the Belgian Governance Institute (GUBERNA) and Manchester Business School.

It builds on the insights of the 10th EU Corporate Governance Conference (December 2010), held under the Belgian Presidency of the EU.

A range of impressive contributions dig deeper into the underlying root causes and critically assess basic international governance assumptions in light of the 2008 fall of Lehman Bros. and subsequent financial crisis.

Special Issue of the Corporate Governance Journal 2010: CR and Governance: The Responsible Corporation in a Global Economy (Emerald Insight)

The 7th EABIS Special Issue of the Corporate Governance Journal builds on the 8th Annual Colloquium held in Barcelona, where IESE Business School staged an excellent conference. The publication explores the global and corporate governance dimensions of the business in society debate, underpinned

by excellent inputs from – among others – Peter Loescher, CEO of Siemens, Bruno Berthon, MD Sustainability Accenture, Philippe Haspeslagh, Dean of Vlerick Management School, and Jan Aart Scholte of Warwick University.

Special Issue of the Corporate Governance Journal 2011: Corporate Responsibility and Emerging Markets

This Special Issue draws on the thought leadership from EABIS' first ever Colloquium hosted in an emerging market, courtesy of St. Petersburg Graduate School of Management. With contributions from luminaries such as Jean-Pierre Lehmann and Arthur Appleton (Evian Group), Peter Lacy (Accenture) and Josep Lozano (ESADE), it is another excellent addition to EABIS' knowledge resources.

Membership 2010-2011 – New members

In 2010-2011, EABIS continued its expansion, raising attention and collecting interest from a number of institutions and businesses, which is reflected in our membership increase.

Membership end 2011 (total)

Corporate Partners & Founding Partners	6
Academic Partners & Founding Partners	13
Corporate Members	22
Academic Members	44
Associate Members	16
Affiliate Members	14

Yale University (USA)

Al-Akhawayn (Morocco)
Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (Israel)
Cofra Holding (CHN)
EPPA (BE)
European University (CH)
Exeter (UK)
Hull (UK)

IIM Kerala (IN)
Intel Corporation (US)
Landi Renzo (IT)
Lappeenranta (FI)
Leuphana (DE)
Lingan (CN)
Mannheim (DE)

Nottingham (UK)
Northampton (UK)
Ricoh (JPN)
SKF (SE)
Thamassat (TH)
University of South Pacific (FJ)

American University Cairo (EGY)
Barry University (US)
CEIBS Shanghai (CN)
DePaul University (US)
University of St. Thomas (US)

Global Reporting Initiative (NL)
Foretica (SP)
CSR Asia (CHN)
Agentur Mehrwert (DE)
Japanese Business Forum (JPN)
Challenge: Future (SI)

EABIS: A Global Network for Business-Academic Collaboration

In 2010 & 2011 the EABIS team, with the support and counsel of the Management Board, has continued to focus on both **quality and quantity** – namely the recruitment of new members who have demonstrated excellence and leadership in the mainstreaming of corporate responsibility issues into business theory and practice. For the seventh successive year, membership recruitment and retention plans were met and surpassed. But above all the EABIS community has been strengthened by the addition of global companies, top academic institutions and leading affiliate networks, with the expertise, insight and knowledge resources that they have to offer our mission.

EABIS has over 120 members and reaches 3,500+ businesses through affiliated networks.

EABIS Members Around The World

The EABIS Network now reaches across 26 countries worldwide and across all five continents

Acknowledging Our Founding Partners and Partners

As we enter our second decade of thought leadership and innovation, we would like to acknowledge the invaluable role of EABIS' 19 founding partners and partners in shaping our past, present and future.

Their investment in EABIS over the years – through strategic guidance in The Academy's Supervisory Board, their major contributions to EABIS' financial resources, and their stewardship of our strategic development – has ensured that EABIS today is capable of tackling critical sustainability challenges for business, policy-makers and civil society.

Thanks to the support of our Partners – especially IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell and Unilever – in our first decade EABIS has:

Delivered 50+ knowledge development and learning initiatives

Earned € 5+ million in competitive EU funding to co-ordinate 60% of corporate responsibility research projects funded to date

Secured € 2+ million in investment from EABIS' corporate founding partners and partners

Co-created the United Nations Global Compact Principles for Responsible Management Education

Co-developed with EFMD the "Business in Society Gateway", the world's leading online resource for CR & Sustainability material and educational insights

Influenced the European Commission to move beyond CSR to a business in society agenda in social sciences research

Represented the strategic and intellectual interests of the EABIS network on the EU Multistakeholder Forum for CSR Steering Committee

Conclusions

In the course of the past two years, EABIS as a network has accomplished a remarkable amount, given the dynamics of the economic crisis, resource constraints and rapid international expansion.

Projects such as Valuing Non-Financial Performance, Global Health Decision-Making, Enabling Technologies and Practical Wisdom have all broken new ground – in terms of business-led, stakeholder-supported design and delivery, as well as intellectual ambition.

While we can all take satisfaction from the accomplishments profiled in the last 20 pages, we cannot afford to rest on our collective laurels. The global sustainability agenda demands that we “raise the bar” even higher in a number of critical areas.

In doing so, however, we must balance the ongoing needs of our traditional constituency - namely, Corporate Responsibility managers, researchers and professors - with those leading the global sustainability debate at a systems level. Some of the ways in which we intend to manage this tension are as follow:

Drive corporate growth– bringing more companies into EABIS to enhance our collaborative work, provide new insights into future business needs, and strengthen our network’s expertise around key sectors and issues

Leverage existing knowledge – increasing the profile and recognition of our network’s thought leadership in CR and sustainability to relevant international communities, funding bodies and other stakeholders

Advance interdisciplinary – connecting with a wider range of business functions and academic faculties to shape appropriate responses to knowledge & learning gaps around global sustainability challenges

Champion mainstreaming – focusing on a broader and deeper integration of business in society issues into executive and management development programmes, both in-company and within business schools & universities

Secure new resources – scaling up opportunities for our members to engage in pioneering research and learning projects, whether through the EU, global foundations, regional development agencies or companies

Build high-value partnerships – aligning EABIS with select international organisations to develop new alliances and strategic initiatives that reinforce our network’s leadership in the global business in society debate

02

**Special Features:
Milestones in 2010-2011**

EABIS Events: Experiential Learning Congress

Experiential Learning is an inter-disciplinary approach based in management, education and psychology suggesting a holistic approach to learning. Many companies acknowledge the benefits of a structured approach to HR development which integrates experiential learning in partnership with external organisations.

The first ever EABIS Congress on Experiential Learning organised by EABIS, hosted by **ESMT Berlin** and supported by Agentur Mehrwert and the Robert Bosch Stiftung, took place on November 25-26, 2010. Through a dynamic programme, it sought to explore current experiential learning initiatives, their importance for management education and the relevance for companies aiming to develop and leverage the potential of their employees and leaders.

Insights and content were provided by a wide range of business and academic organisations. Organisations presenting in Berlin included: IBM, Ashridge, EBS European Business School, Oestrich-Winkel, Sound Strategies, streetfootballworld gGmbH, Cass University London, Forum for the Future, BITC, Grenoble Ecole de Management, Lloyds Banking Group, Maastricht University, Universität Duisburg-Essen, European Institute for Industrial Leadership, ESCP Europe, and others.

How does contemporary management education employ Experiential Learning to optimise management development and executive education?

The Congress explored how to integrate experiential learning into the HR development in order to:

- Provide employees with opportunities to exercise skills and capabilities in external environments
- Create learning challenges through (unfamiliar) organisational structures and cultures;
- Present opportunities to develop skills and competences identified for future progression but not otherwise tested in the employees' current role;
- Encourage better teambuilding and collaborative working within business units and/or across leadership and management cohorts through project-based interim consultancy and 'volunteering' programmes
- Support internal career progression and associated restructuring issues by providing temporary 'out' secondments.

Beyond the benefits for employees and philanthropic support for local community organisations, the Congress concluded that programmes for supporting and encouraging experiential learning may also:

- Raise the levels of employee engagement through facilitating better work-life balance;
- Enhance the company's *licence to operate* through more effective stakeholder engagement;
- Increased marketing and PR capability delivered by encouraging employees as local community champions;
- Provide better outreach through well-informed community and/or sponsorship programmes.

EABIS Events: 2011 Annual Colloquium

A new era of development: the changing role & responsibilities of business in developing countries

During the last few years, profound shifts have taken place in geopolitics and economic power. The rise in “south-south” trade has challenged the hegemony of western norms in trade and business such as **transparency, governance and ethics**. And while more business is being done in developing countries, there is little agreement about the **responsibilities of business in development**.

At the same time food, health, poverty and education issues as well as corruption and bribery in developing countries require urgent action. **The response from business to these challenges** will be potentially the single most important factor in determining whether a new era of development achieves the objective of sustainable and inclusive growth.

During the 27/28 October 2011, 300 participants joined the 10th Annual EABIS Colloquium to discuss two major challenges to business in developing countries :

1. The definition of strategies and partnerships that enhance sustainability of business and market development;
2. The need to innovate to deliver profitable products and services in developing countries.

While many possible themes arise from these two challenges, the Colloquium focused on:

- Taking stock of successes and failures in development over the past 50 years
- Identifying the major factors that will underpin a new era of development
- Showcasing business innovation in response to critical challenges in developing countries
- Shaping a new agenda for integrating development in management practice, research & education

Following the call for contributions, over 80 case studies from the field and research insights relating to the role of business in development and developing countries were presented.

Fields covered, among others, were: social enterprises, value-added reporting, responsibility and legitimacy, sustainable business administration, business in conflict areas, corruption, inequalities, multinationals addressing poverty, business-NGO partnerships, employee engagement, microfinance, community engagement, sustainable innovation.

EABIS Events: 2011 Annual Colloquium

Speakers

Henrietta Elizabeth Thompson – Assistant Secretary-General, United Nations & Executive Coordinator, UN Conference on Sustainable Development Rio+20
Pierre Jacquet – Chief Economist, Agence Française de Développement & Professor, Ecole des Ponts-ParisTech
Sophie Gasperment – Executive Chairman, The Body Shop
Jane Griffiths – Company Group Chair (EMEA) & Global Sustainability Lead, Johnson & Johnson Pharmaceuticals
Javier Irarrazaval – Managing Director Chile, Walt Disney Co. & President, Forum EMPRESA
Peter Davis – Research Fellow, Overseas Development Institute
Nazeer Ladhani – Director, Graduate Professional Education, Aga Khan University Kenya
Jermyn Brooks – Chair, Global Network Initiative & Transparency International Business Advisory Board
Leif Sjöblom – Professor in Financial Management, IMD Lausanne
Carsten Völz – Humanitarian Director, Oxfam International
Ravi Fernando – International Director for Europe, Singapore Economic Development Board
Kamal Ahmad – Founder & Acting Vice Chancellor, Asian University for Women
CB Bhattacharya – E.ON Chair in Corporate Responsibility, ESMT Berlin
Lourdes Casanova – Lecturer in Strategy, INSEAD
Pierre Nanterme – CEO, Accenture
Dipak C. Jain – Dean, INSEAD
Christophe Yvetot – UNIDO Representative to the EU & Head of UNIDO Office in Brussels
Daniel Traça – NOVAFORUM Professor of Sustainable International Business, NOVA School of Business & Economics
Raj Brown – Emeritus Professor of International Business, Royal Holloway University of London
Mark Esposito – Founder & Director, Lab-Center for Competitiveness, EM Grenoble
Fredrik Galtung – Chief Executive Officer, Tiri
Henri-Claude de Bettignies – Aviva Chair Emeritus Professor of Leadership and Responsibility, INSEAD
Stefan Schepers – Managing Partner EPPA, hon. Director General European Institute Public Administration
Pedro Montoya – EADS Group Chief Compliance Officer
Craig Smith – Chaired Professor of Ethics & Social Responsibility, INSEAD
Cláudio Bruzzi Boechat – Professor, Núcleo Petrobras de Sustentabilidade, Fundação Dom Cabral
Chris Knight – Director, Forestry and Ecosystems, PricewaterhouseCoopers
Chris Perceval – Corporate Relations Director, World Resources Institute
Ans Kolk – Research Director & Professor in Sustainable Management, University of Amsterdam Business School
Ricarda McFalls – Chief, Multinational Enterprises Programme, Job Creation and Enterprise Development Department, ILO
Stefaan Van der Borghet – Director, Global Health Affairs Heineken International
Sir Henry Burns – Chief Medical Officer for Scotland
Steven Le Poole – Co-Founder, Max Foundation
Michael Cannon-Brookes – Vice President, Global Strategy, IBM Growth Markets
Doug Baillie – Chief Human Resources Officer, Unilever PLC
Sir John Holmes – Director, The Ditchley Foundation & Former UN Emergency Relief Coordinator
Jordi Canals – Dean, IESE
Walter Baets – Director, Graduate School of Business, University of Cape Town
Ted Roosevelt Malloch – Chairman, The Roosevelt Group & Research Professor for Spiritual Capital Initiative, Yale University
Mark Lee Hunter – Adjunct Professor and Senior Research Fellow, INSEAD
Jan Muehlfeit – Chairman Europe, Microsoft Corporation
Gilbert Lenssen – President, EABIS
Luk Van Wassenhove – INSEAD Colloquium Chair

INSEAD

The Business School
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EABIS Events: Symposium on Corporate Responsibility and Innovation

The symposium was part of the ESC Dijon - Burgundy Sustainability Week on 1-7 April promoted by the French Ministry of Sustainable Development. The Sustainability Week features a series of conferences and workshops organised in partnership with Le Groupe de La Poste and EDF.

The key focus areas of the programme was on sustainability-driven innovation, management innovation, entrepreneurship and SMEs, organisational learning and change. These areas reflect a broader context which was explored during the plenary sessions :

Plenary I – Sustainability challenges as a driver for innovation

How do multinational companies integrate pressures and trends in their global business environment into their strategic planning and decision-making?

Plenary II - Organizational innovation for sustainable value creation

How do companies harness sustainability issues to develop and embed new business models, processes, technologies and systems? How do they understand and measure the impact on corporate performance (social and financial), and benefits for key stakeholders?

Plenary III - Leadership of innovation and implications for executive development

How do organisations capture and learn from the process(es) of innovation and change around sustainability? How are these insights translated into management and executive development frameworks?

Keynotes

Walid Malouf, Clinton Foundation, Urban Sustainability Challenges, Market Opportunities and the Role of Not for Profit Change Agents.

David Bevan, EABIS & Grenoble Graduate School of Business, Sustainability and Innovation as Strategic Operating Principles: the Case of MTR (Hong Kong)

Georges Lefebvre, Groupe La Poste, Faire Coexister une Stratégie de Développement et d'un Engagement RSE Affirmé : l'Exemple du Modèle Social du Groupe La Poste

Luis Torras, EADA, Building a CSR Strategy

Jacques Spelkens, GDF Suez, How Can Social Innovative Actions in Line with the Group's Strategy Contribute to a Sustainable Business Model?

Alexandra Stubbings, Ashridge Business School, The Organisational Conditions Required to Support Sustainable Innovative Practice and Thinking Inside Organizations: the Role of Leaders

Thomas Osburg, Intel, Strategic CSR – Challenges for Management Development and How to Address Those Through Strategic University Partnerships

Steven MacGregor, IESE Business School, Sustainable Executive Performance: Unlocking the Door to Sustainability Mainstreaming?

EABIS Events: Practical Wisdom

Conferences included in a conference cycle on Practical Wisdom organised by EABIS in partnership with Yale and supported by EFMD.

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Chinese Classical Traditions, 18-19 June 2010, China Europe International Business School, Shanghai

Chinese culture increasingly will permeate international culture and move from peripheral to mainstream status. To ignore this in management education would be a grave oversight.

The conference offered insight into the various streams of thought within the classical Chinese traditions and their contemporary relevance.

Special Issue : Journal of Management Development, Vol. 30 Issue 7/8 - 2011 ([available online](#))

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Jewish Tradition, 4-6 July 2011, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev

Clearly, the question of managerial action will be of primary importance during the conference. If the Jewish tradition can be a source of practical wisdom, then it must be a cornerstone of activities which are inspired by the idea of putting oneself at the service of others. This is why the notion of social leadership will be tackled from several points of view during the conference.

Ben-Gurion University of the Negev
אוניברסיטת בן-גוריון בנגב

Forthcoming Special Issue, Journal of Management Development, Vol. 31, Issue 9 – October 2012

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Islamic Tradition, 17-18 November 2011 Al Akhawayn University in Ifrane, Morocco

The relevance of this tradition is due to the influence of Islam at the beginning of the 21st century. Islam is the fastest growing religion in the world with 1.5 billion adherents, many of whom live in fast-growing economies with young populations.

Future changes in the world's economy and demography will only continue to increase the importance of Muslim business practices.

Further, Islamic business ethics itself is unique. As Muhammad himself lived the life of a salesman and charismatic leader the Qur'an is probably the religious document which is most explicit on normative questions of business practice.

Forthcoming Special Issue , Journal of Management Development, Vol. 31, Issue 10 – October 2012

EABIS Corporate Partner Project: Advancing Global Health Decision-Making

Mapping the landscape of health decision making (Rutgers, May 2011)

The aim of the EABIS-Rutgers-Johnson & Johnson AGHDM initiative is to create an international platform for advancing the quality and impact of institutional decision-making. It will focus in particular on enhanced sharing, use and interpretation of data on global health challenges, as well as building capacity for coordination and collaboration across public, private, and civic sectors.

Throughout 2011 (and ongoing in 2012) the programme has engaged a select group of leaders – from business, government, academia and civil society – who understand the complexities of these decision-making processes, and who share a strategic commitment to advancing health and wellness in developed and developing markets alike. Its objective is to generate a co-designed, forward-looking agenda for research and innovation that will inspire and inform business strategy, policy formulation, civic activity and education.

In May 2011 we convened around 80 participants for our initial conference (at Rutgers University). Many of those present have since remarked that the event was one of the more enriching and stimulating experiences that they could recall. It is clear from their comments that four aspects of the process and structure were key:

- 1) An open process focused on creating and capturing ideas;
- 2) The emphasis on decision-making as our central theme;
- 3) The diverse range of international experts present; and
- 4) The spirit of openness, trust and collaboration that infused both days.

The first workshop also served as a launch pad for working groups among participants, which were tasked with defining more specific areas of a forward-looking knowledge development and innovation agenda to be presented and reviewed at Fontainebleau in October 2011

Drilling deeper into health decision making (CEPED, Oct 2011)

The CEPED conference built on the successful launch which took place at Rutgers University in May 2011, which was hailed by many of the participants as one of the more enriching and stimulating fora that they had experienced in recent years.

In this context the 2nd conference (re)united many of the original group with a select number of additional experts to further enhance the quality of discussion and scoping of future scenarios. Our focus at CEPED was primarily on the following:

- Summary of the “red threads” identified in New Brunswick across all dimensions of AGHDM;
- Review of the key questions (and partial answers) generated by the working groups;
- Identification of good practices and evidence bases in line with these questions;
- Discussion of potential “bridges” to other organizations and networks which might have a strategic interest in and/or help to scale AGHDM outputs;
- Individual commitments to action in taking the AGHDM outputs forward (research proposals, international dialogue, etc).

EABIS members organisations involved

Bentley University | CEIBS Shanghai | Copenhagen Business School | CSR Europe
Heineken International | IBM | INSEAD | Johnson & Johnson
Kingston University Business School | Manchester Business School | Microsoft | Rutgers University
SDA Bocconi School of Management | St Petersburg State University | TNT Global
University of Cape Town | Witten / Herdecke University

EABIS Partnership Project: Valuing Non-Financial Performance

Valuing non-financial performance is a collaborative project with CSR Europe and led by companies including EABIS members Solvay, Telecom Italia and Lloyds Banking Group. It emerged from the previous Laboratory on Valuing Non-Financial Performance which was also supported by a parallel research group, funded by EABIS' Corporate Partners Programme, including Cranfield School of Management, SDA Bocconi and Vlerick Leuven Ghent.

In its final practitioner report published at EABIS' 2010 Leaders Forum, the Laboratory made a number of recommendations to different stakeholders. There were three to the European Commission:

1. To convene a vanguard group of companies and investors willing to take a lead in publicly committing to explain how they are committed to improving and analysing core areas of non-financial performance;
2. Use the dialogue between companies, investors and other stakeholders on ESG performance to incubate the international accounting standards bodies' exploration of integrating non-financial drivers in recognised reporting standards;
3. Fund training for companies, analysts and investors in how to evaluate non-financial performance and its relevance to corporate strategy and management processes.

Recommendations 2 and 3 were followed up. The Commission's ESG working group was a catalyst for the emergence of the International Integrated Reporting Council. The Commission also granted monies in 2011 for development of analyst and investor training.

The collaborative project built on the momentum created by the Laboratory. It has two workstreams:

1. A company project investigating the measurement and management of non-financial performance in the pursuit of improvement in both and a rationale for greater alignment with strategy and key business results
2. An investor project comprising major asset managers, asset owners and advisers in identifying the most material non-financial drivers of financial performance (and its ESG underpinnings) based on established causal financial relationships or significant evidence of such relationships.

The company project currently involves around 30 companies engaged in a series of individual in-company and collective workshops over 2011 and 2012. These are focused on developing better management and measurement, integration in company operations and processes and strategic alignment of non-financial performance.

The investor project – Project Delphi – now involves around 50 major asset managers and asset owners. A working group led by the European Federation of Financial Analysts' Societies has developed a framework for dialogue based on the work of the Laboratory to enable sharing of intellectual property between the asset managers in pursuit of convergence around the key drivers of non-financial performance and associated metrics. Once consensus has been obtained around a final framework, it will be tested with asset owners. It is hoped that a final report will be published in the first half of 2013.

The collaborative nature of the project ensures that the two parallel workstreams are maintaining active dialogue. The synergies in exploration and findings will be mutually reinforcing. The deliberations and outcomes will also feed into EABIS' thematic focus on sustainable finance in 2012 and 2013.

GOLDEN: Organisational Learning for Sustainability

The GOLDEN challenge

For companies to effectively respond to increasing resource constraints and stakeholder expectations requires both deep foresight knowledge and capacity to change. This knowledge and capacity must reflect four uncomfortable truths:

- Sustainability challenges will grow in complexity and diversity;
- No company can do it by itself – competitive dynamics require a systemic approach;
- There is a big gap in our knowledge about *how* to move corporations powerfully and effectively towards sustainability;

The source of sustainability lies with fundamental change in organizations' culture and individuals' leadership style.

As well as these truths, companies also face short-term orientation of investors and managers; risk-, diversity- and change-averse organizational cultures; and unproven "recipes" for success. Moreover, there is insufficient understanding about which change strategies are most effective and under which conditions. This raises a daunting question: *How to bring about profound change, while ensuring both short- and long-term value creation.*

The GOLDEN response

GOLDEN is carrying out three interdependent activities. Each has products that are of value in their own right, and each also contributes to the development of the other activities. They arise from an understanding about how to realize large systems change:

1. The Global Observatory on the Evolution of the Sustainable Enterprise (the "Observatory"): This is the global data platform of GOLDEN, that holds data from its other activities. This data is also used in the activities, and can be used to answer other questions. The aim is to create an unparalleled data and knowledge platform about sustainability practices.

2. Three "Future labs" to address the change challenge at the three levels that are required to be effective. Each begins with an assessment, followed by an experiment or intervention that draws from hypotheses that arise with the assessment, and then draws conclusions about the hypotheses. These occur at three levels, reflecting GOLDEN's change theory;

- Eco-system Labs: a series of multi-stakeholder dialogues aimed at the definition of the "enterprise of the future" in the eco-systems of interest
- Enterprise Labs: the observation and impact assessment of a firm's change interventions designed with rigorous experimental methods
- Decision Maker Labs: the observation and impact assessment of training interventions for decision-makers in firms, stakeholders and policy-makers

3. A multi-level simulation model that will use the **GOLDEN** data to develop forecasts of the impact of specific strategy and policy choices.

EABIS has supported the development of the GOLDEN project involving a number of our member research centres and companies. EABIS is represented in the GOLDEN advisory board.

EABIS Thought Leadership Dialogue: Corporate Responsibility, Brand, Reputation and Consumer Perceptions

Do consumers define the purpose of the firm?

Paul Polman, Unilever CEO, caused much comment when he told the Financial Times in 2010, “I do not work for the shareholder, to be honest; I work for the consumer, the customer.”

He further elaborated in launching Unilever’s Sustainable Living Plan, “We are already finding that tackling sustainability challenges provides new opportunities for sustainable growth: it creates preference for our brands, builds business with our retail customers, drives our innovation, grows our markets and, in many cases, generates cost savings.”

EABIS’s 2011 Senior Leaders’ Forum, held in Brussels on June 15, explored the role of the consumer in defining the purpose of the firm. It focused on a number of key questions:

- What do we know about consumer perceptions of business and brands?
- How are those perceptions informing the development of business models?
- What impact do sustainability issues have on business brand and reputation?
- How can business harness their response to those sustainability issues to influence consumer perception, consideration and advocacy?
- How will this be translated into market and product development?

Over 80 corporate and academic members and invited commentators heard and discussed a range of presentations addressing these questions. The outputs from the day, including presentations, have been published in EABIS’ 3rd Thought Leadership publication.

Although the conclusions were often unclear, it is evident that the perceptions of consumers are subject to change and corporate responsibility and sustainability are a driver of change. That fact that companies are both responding to consumers (often influenced by pressures from media or regulatory authorities) or finding it

necessary to shape consumer perceptions in favour of new or re-engineered products, demonstrates the agenda’s salience.

As a result, brand, reputation and consumer perceptions will be an EABIS thematic focus in 2012 and beyond. In 2012, we will have the launch of the Corporate Founding Partners funded research, undertaken by Insead, on consumer perceptions and the ‘halo effect’. EABIS is also delivering a number of company workshops with corporate partner, Ketchum Pleon, on stakeholder perceptions and the value of brand and reputation.

03

**EABIS Operational
Review 2010-2011**

Resources

Renewed existing financial resources and funding

In 2011, all six Corporate Founding & Corporate Partners – IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell and Unilever – agreed to renew their funding commitment to EABIS at a level equivalent or superior to the funds invested from 2008 to 2010 (between € 400 – 450K per annum). This is a major affirmation of the unique value offered by EABIS' collaborative business-academic model.

Through extended discussions with each partner, tailored Corporate Partner Knowledge and Learning Programmes have been, and continue to be designed and rolled out with the active involvement of our academic partners and members.

Expanded financial resources and funding

In the past 2 years, EABIS has devoted increased time and energy to build bridges with key European policy institutions to explore possibilities for securing funds to support member initiatives. These efforts have resulted in:

€ 2.6 million for “CSR Impact Performance and Measurement” (a.k.a. The “IMPACT” Project) from DG Research & Innovation under the European Union's 7th Framework Programme for Research;

In January 2012 EABIS also submitted a bid for € 2.5 million for “Innovation for Sustainability (I4S)”, from DG Research & Innovation under the European Union's MARIE CURIE Initial Training Network Programme to support business-relevant doctoral research;

The EABIS central team has supported over 30 individual members in a range of tenders for FP7 funding, and continues to monitor Calls from different DGs to identify opportunities in line with EABIS' focus and capabilities.

In addition, EABIS has begun to map out the international foundation space with a view to securing additional grants for new knowledge & learning initiatives. We have also received a \$ 1.5. million grant secured from a leading North American Foundation to support expansion until 2014.

EABIS central team has been regularly reinforced with interns from The Leonardo da Vinci Programme which funds practical projects in the field of vocational education and training.

Expanded Human and Knowledge Capital Resources

In 2010-2011, EABIS further expanded the capacity of its central team by confirming Prof. Ted Roosevelt Malloch (Yale University) as its first ever Director Americas and Andre Habisch (KU Eichstaett-Ingolstadt) as Associate Research Director, recruiting Joris-Johann Lenssen as Research Manager, and by expanding the support capacity in Brussels through different EU internship schemes. The team has been further supplemented through the relationship with Ketchum Pleon, which has seconded a senior consultant to the EABIS central team since December 2009 – an invaluable part of upscaling the corporate value proposition!

Strategic Partnerships

Strategic Partnerships

UNITED NATIONS GLOBAL COMPACT PRINCIPLES FOR RESPONSIBLE MANAGEMENT EDUCATION (PRME)

Since 2007 EABIS has been a founding member of the UN PRME Steering Committee, supporting the creation and development of this important framework that now has over 350 signatory institutions worldwide. Our commitment is a reflection of our mission – and those of our members – to enhancing the quality and relevance of executive development through active dialogue with and engagement of leading companies and other stakeholders.

It is from this business-led perspective that EABIS lends its active support to the further development of PRME. The social, environmental, governance and economic challenges facing companies today are clearly coalescing into a global agenda. Two projects have been explicitly dedicated to PRME to address this.

EUROPEAN FOUNDATION FOR MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT (EFMD)

EABIS – The Academy of Business in Society and the European Foundation for Management Development (EFMD) entered into a strategic partnership in early 2006. Our longstanding alliance has established a significant platform for the mainstreaming of business in society issues into management education in Europe and beyond.

EFMD supports the realisation of the goals of EABIS and contributes to specific events and projects, while EABIS supports EFMD in advancing the Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability agenda with its membership. At the governance level, Prof. Eric Cornuel, EFMD Director General, is a member of the EABIS Supervisory Board, while EABIS President Prof. Gilbert Lenssen served on the EFMD Board from 2003 to 2009.

CSR EUROPE

EABIS and CSR Europe share a ten-year strategic relationship that goes back to the creation of The Academy. In the past decade, the two organisations have collaborated on a variety of projects and initiatives, including the CSR Platform, EU CSR Alliance (Valuing Non-Financial Performance Laboratory) and EU Multi-Stakeholder Forum for CSR.

As EABIS revisits its founding mission and mandate to shape the next 10 years of activity, and as CSR Europe formalises the structure and core activities of Enterprise 2020, both organisations are committed to exploring tangible ways in which the two organisations can contribute to and enhance the value of each other's strategic positioning and initiatives.

The foundations for increased dialogue and collaboration has already been discussed with Viscount Davignon, with a proposal in place for the Chair of CSR Europe to be invited to EABIS' Supervisory Board Meetings and a reciprocal invitation for EABIS' President to join CSR Europe's Strategic Steering Group for E2020 (both in an *ex officio* capacity).

EABIS Governance Structure

Key: = Direction of Accountability

Governance Representatives

EABIS Governance positions at end 2011

Chair: Viscount Etienne Davignon
(also Vice-Chair, GDF Suez)

President: Prof. Dr. Gilbert Lenssen

Director General: Simon Pickard

Executive Director: John Swannick

Academic Director: David Bevan

SUPERVISORY BOARD

Chair: Etienne Davignon – **Vice Chairs:** Doug Baillie, Unilever; Jan Muehlfeit, Microsoft; Dipak Jain, INSEAD; Alfons Sauquet, ESADE; Andrew Kakabadse, Cranfield School of Management; Baron André Van Heemstra, EABIS; **Members:** Gilbert Lenssen, EABIS (ex officio); Michael Burkhardt, IBM; Frank Welvaert, Johnson & Johnson; Garnt Louw, Shell; Tim de Boer, Ketchum Pleon; Stefan Schepers, EPPA; Kai Peters, Ashridge; Dorte Salskov-Iversen, Copenhagen; Jordi Canals, IESE; Dominique Turpin, IMD; Sir Andrew Likierman, London; Michael Luger, Manchester; Alberto Grando, SDA Bocconi; Philippe Haspeslagh, Vlerick & Audit Committee Chair; Mark P. Taylor, Warwick; Ted Malloch, Yale University; Chris Marsden, Business and Human Rights Resource Centre; Mark Wade, Future Considerations; Eric Cornuel, EFMD; Peter Lacy, Accenture; Elena Bonfiglioli, Microsoft.

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Chair: Gilbert Lenssen, EABIS; **Business Network Chair:** Michel Bande, Solvay; **Academic Network Chair:** Nigel Roome, Vlerick and TiasNimbas; **Vice Chairs:** Katinka van Cranenburgh, Heineken; Mike Patrick, TNT; Elisabeth Crone Jensen, Copenhagen; Francesco Perrini, SDA Bocconi; **Members:** Thomas Osburg, Intel Europe; Matthew Neilson, Unilever, Joan Fontrodona, IESE; Nicola Pless, ESADE; Stefan Crets, CSR Europe; Simon Pickard, EABIS.

ACADEMIC NETWORK BOARD

Chair: Nigel Roome, Vlerick; **Vice Chairs:** Elisabeth Crone Jensen, Copenhagen; Francesco Perrini, SDA Bocconi; **Members:** Nicola Pless, ESADE; Joan Fontrodona, IESE; Marianna Fotaki, Manchester; Malcolm McIntosh, Griffith; Stephanie Giamcamporcaro, Cape Town; Andre Sobczak, Audencia Nantes; Mick Blowfield, London; Tomas Mandakovic, Barry; Lutz Preuss, Royal Holloway; Celine Louche, Vlerick..

BUSINESS NETWORK BOARD

Chair: Michel Bande, Solvay; **Vice Chairs:** Mike Patrick, TNT; Katinka van Cranenburgh, Heineken International; **Members:** Matthew Neilson, Unilever; Thomas Osburg, Intel Europe; Paolo Nazzaro, Telecom Italia.

The EABIS Team and Global Resources

EABIS Central Team (today)

Gilbert Lenssen, President
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John Swannick, Executive Director
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Raquel Petra Lopes, Communications Coordinator
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Ludwig Roger, Executive Coordinator
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John Hager, Operations Coordinator
John.hager@eabis.org

EABIS Global Resources

Viscount Etienne Davignon, Chairman
Prof Gilbert Lenssen, President

Brussels (new office - Avenue Molière 128, Ixelles, Brussels)

Simon Pickard, Director General
Dr Christiane Malcorps, Executive Director, Senior Vice President Solvay (on full secondment)
Dr Jacqueline Brassey-Schouten, Senior Fellow, Associate Research Director (part time)
Joris Lenssen, Research Manager
Cristian Loza Adai, Research Fellow and Project Manager (part time)
Raquel Lopes, Communications Coordinator
Ludwig Roger, Executive Coordinator (part time)
Elena Urizar, Projects Coordinator
John Hager, Operations Coordinator
+ Post-doctoral researchers from China
+ Post-doctoral researcher from EU *Marie Curie*-funded PhD project

London

John Swannick, Corporate Director

Eichstaett

Prof Andre Habisch, Associate Research Director (part time, also KU Eichstaett-Ingolstadt)

Chicago

Prof Mollie Painter-Morland, Academic Director (half time in each location)

New York (office provided by Greenberg Traug, International Law Firm & New Member)

Prof Ted Roosevelt Malloch, Director Americas (also Yale University)

Shanghai (office provided by InnoCSR, Consultancy & New Member)

Sam Lee, Director Asia (part time, also InnoCSR)
Prof David Bevan, Associate Research Director (part time, also CEIBS Shanghai)

Brisbane

Prof Malcolm MacIntosh, Coordinator of APABIS integration (part time, also Griffith University Business School)

Cape Town – Brussels

Dr Stefan Schepers, Director Asia (also EPPA)

Rio de Janeiro

Claudia Kipka, Regional Coordinator South America (from September 2012, part time)

04

**EABIS in 2012:
Starting Our Second Decade**

Renewing Our Mission & Strengthening as a Unique Global Platform

Renewing Our Mission & Strengthening as a Unique Global Platform

EABIS remains a **unique global alliance of companies, business schools and other institutions** committed to promoting more sustainable business practice through partnership, learning and research. As we enter our second decade, we will continue to:

Facilitate	Communicate	Engage
<p>Shared learning opportunities Platforms to showcase practice and thinking Partnerships to address learning, research and operational needs Funding propositions for collaborative research and learning projects</p>	<p>Opportunities for collaboration with other members and strategic partners Intelligence on current trends, major issues and relevant themes for sustainable business Updates and access to our rich online knowledge and information resource</p>	<p>Members in developing individual route maps to maximise relationship benefits Professional, trade and other membership organisations in building strategic partnerships Policy makers in defining the agenda for sustainable business.</p>

EABIS is a reference point for organisations seeking access to leading edge thinking and practice in corporate responsibility, sustainability and governance – as recognised by major supranational institutions, not least the European Commission and the United Nations Global Compact. Our members:

Innovate	Influence	Inspire
<p>Seizing opportunities for personal and organisational learning Taking current ideas and approaches and testing them against others' best practice and emerging thinking Working with partners to develop solutions to the key challenges we face</p>	<p>Content and delivery of mainstream business education and research Thinking of policy makers to better enable sustainable business Their reputation as leaders in sustainable business practice and thinking.</p>	<p>Learning from their experience in implementation of new approaches Change in the quality of debate on sustainable business Others to follow thought and practice leadership</p>

Constructing Four Pillars of Activity

International growth is driving an expanded value proposition based on new models of activity, collaboration and partnership around four key pillars of activity:

Our values in all activities and projects:

- Business relevance
- Academic rigour
- Policy insight
- Interdisciplinary
- Mainstreaming
- Creative solutions

EABIS Thought Leadership 2012 and Beyond...

So what awaits the EABIS network in 2012 and beyond? Above all, we are planning a year of expansion in a number of strategically important areas, based on our capabilities of operational excellence and intellectual innovation:

- **Advancing our Member Value Proposition and delivery.**
- **Advancing our global membership** with a specific focus on China, North America, India and South America.
- **Advancing our engagement with global companies** to provide strategic value through tailored collaboration with academic members by region.
- **Advancing our thought leadership & intellectual scope** through events, projects, grant proposals and publications on (among others):
 - Taking Stock of 10 Years of Mainstreaming Progress
 - Chief Learning Officers and Executive Development
 - Advancing Health Decision-Making
 - Innovation for Sustainability
 - The Role of MNCs in Addressing Global Development Challenges
 - Management Education for Sustainability in Africa
 - Social Entrepreneurship for Innovative Societies
 - Sustainable lifestyles & The Green Economy
 - Sustainability and Finance
- **Expanding our efforts to support education and learning** – with a specific focus on PhD, young researcher and faculty development.
- **Expanding our pursuit of funding opportunities and resources: “The Next Ten Million”** – with a focus on the EU and global foundations.

Looking Ahead to 2012 and Beyond...

Overall, we can say that EABIS is in robust financial health and thriving intellectual spirits going forwards in 2012. In order to deliver on our objectives, we will seek to draw on your support, expertise, commitment and vision at various stages in the process.

Regarding our Annual Colloquium – the conference will travel to Switzerland for the first time in 2012, where IMD will host in Lausanne on July 2-4. Our central theme this year will be **Strategic Innovation for Sustainability**. In keeping with tradition, the Annual PhD Conference will follow immediately after the Colloquium on July 5, when Ecole Hoteliere de Lausanne will stage the day-long event.

Internationalisation of The Academy

In the space of a decade, EABIS has grown from its 12 Founding Partners, with predominantly European roots, into a global platform of 130+ firms, business schools, universities and affiliated partners, spread across the five continents.

Since the advent of the financial crisis, EABIS' recruitment focus – and related growth – has been primarily in Asia, North America and Australasia, with the full encouragement of the Supervisory Board. Corporate partners and members are increasingly interested

in the dual potential of the network to address their strategic challenges in a more tailored, localized context, as well as to draw insight and expertise from a worldwide community to explore solutions around specific issues or themes.

1. Against this backdrop, the 2011 General Assembly (October 26, Fontainebleau) has tasked the Management Board and team of Directors to design new models for member engagement and activity in other regions or continents. While this remains an evolving process, some notable steps had already been taken by the end of the year towards this objective: Integration of non-members which were members of the Asia-Pacific Academy of Business in Society (APABIS);
2. Appointment of EABIS' first Directors (part-time) in Asia and the Americas;
3. Provisional deal in place to open an EABIS Asia office in Shanghai in 2012;
4. Provisional deal in place to open an EABIS Americas office in New York in 2012;

Further regional objectives in 2012-2013 are likely to include continued growth in China and the US, as well as an in-depth analysis of strategic development prospects in India, South America, the Middle East and

Africa. Ultimately, the success of our ongoing internationalization, and the related shift towards regional platforms, will hinge on some key factors:

- Deepening strategic relationships with existing corporate partners and members;
- Development of a regional corporate agenda and terminology that underlines EABIS' differentiation from existing networks and provides a unique framework for collaboration with academic members;
- Partnering with like-minded, innovative, ambitious organizations which offer the possibility of achieving scale and impact in given projects;
- Connecting individuals and institutions around the world in a reliable, (cost-) effective way to support global exchanges of perspective and knowledge.

New office – Brussels

EABIS global expansion is supported by the central team in Brussels, which has also grown in number, especially in the last year.

Taking advantage of this wind of change, from August 2012 EABIS team in Brussels will be located in a new address:

Avenue Molière 128
1050 Ixelles
Brussels, Belgium

Upcoming Highlights: Events 2012

JAN

Practical Wisdom from the Indian Traditions conference, Indian Institute of Management in Kozhikode, India
EABIS Decennial event, hosted by Nottingham University Business School, UK

FEB

Leuphana Sustainability Summit, Centre for Sustainability Management and EABIS, Lüneburg
CSR Research Seminar: Shaping the future of CSR research, Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School, Louvain School of Management and EABIS, Leuven.

APR

Experiential Learning Congress, hosted by Novancia Business School , Paris

MAY

IMPACT Project: Stakeholder, Policy and Advisory board meeting, EABIS, Brussels
Cross-sector social partnerships symposium, RSM Erasmus University, Hull University Business School and EABIS, Rotterdam

JUN

Webinar 'Strategic Innovation for Sustainability', IMD and EABIS

JUL

10th EABIS Annual PhD Conference, EHL, Lausanne
11th EABIS Annual Colloquium, IMD, Lausanne

SEPT

Australasian Membership Meeting at The Natural Transition 2012 Conference, Asia-Pacific Centre for Sustainable Enterprise, Griffith University, Brisbane

OCT

Wisdom at Work, Sam M. Walton, College of Business, USA

NOV

3rd Advancing Global Health Decision-Making Conference, Johnson&Johnson, EABIS, Africa
Building the Sustainability Investment Case, Nyenrode Business University
Practical Wisdom for Management and Economics from the Buddhist Traditions , EABIS, Yale University , EFMD and Thammasat Business School, Bangkok

Upcoming Highlights: Events 2013

JAN

1st North America Deans Forum: Re-Thinking Faith-Based Management Institutions for the 21st Century, Loyola University, New Orleans*
IMPACT Project: Final Policy and Stakeholder Round Tables, EABIS, Brussels
Submission Deadline for EU FP7 Research Proposals

FEB

IMPACT Project: Final Meeting of Advisory Board, EABIS, Brussels

MAR

Launch of EABIS Asian Regional Platform, Shanghai, China *
Launch of EABIS Global Education Framework, EABIS, Brussels *
Launch of EABIS Global PhD Platform, EABIS, Brussels*

APR

Launch of EABIS North American Regional Platform, New York*
Launch Event for "I4S" Innovation for Sustainability PhD Network Project, Copenhagen *

MAY

Annual Leaders Forum & IMPACT Project Final Conference, EABIS, Brussels

JUN

Closing Conference for Phase I of Practical Wisdom for Management Project, Yale University, New Haven
4th Global Forum of UN PRME, CEEMAN and IEDC Business School, Bled

OCT

11th EABIS Annual PhD Conference, University of Amsterdam Business School, Amsterdam*
12th EABIS Annual Colloquium: Sustainability and Finance, Nyenrode University, Nyenrode
Global Leadership Development in the Chinese Context, CELAP, Pudong*

* Provisional date

Upcoming Highlights: EABIS Publications for 2012-2013

Taking Stock of 10 Years of Mainstreaming Corporate Responsibility

Business & Professional Ethics Journal – expected June 2012

Practical Wisdom from the Islamic Traditions

Journal of Management Development – expected Summer 2012

Practical Wisdom from the Jewish Traditions

Journal of Management Development – expected Summer 2012

Outcomes from EABIS CEO Survey and 3rd EABIS-EFMD Global Deans Survey

Executive Report – expected Autumn 2012

Implementing Social and Environmental Policies in Supply Chains

Practitioner Report and Case Studies – expected Summer 2012

Outcomes from 3rd EABIS-EFMD Global Deans Survey

Special Issue of “Global Focus” magazine – expected Autumn 2012

Integrating Corporate Responsibility in Central and Eastern Europe

Case Studies and Teaching Notes – expected Autumn 2012

Consumer Perceptions of Corporate Responsibility

Practitioner Report and Working Papers – expected Autumn 2012

Corporate Responsibility and the Role of Business in Development

Corporate Governance Journal – expected October 2012

Practical Wisdom from the Indian Classical Traditions

Journal of Management Development – expected Winter 2012

Mainstreaming CR and Sustainability in Executive Education

Textbook and Case Studies – expected Spring 2013

Strategic Innovation for Sustainability

Corporate Governance Journal – expected Autumn 2013

Practical Wisdom from Buddhist Classical Traditions

Journal of Management Development – expected Autumn 2013

Practical Wisdom for Management from the Spiritual and Philosophical Traditions: Corporate Case Studies from Around the World

Yale-EABIS Joint Textbook from Emerald Insight, expected publication in Spring 2013

05

Financial Review

Report for Financial Year 2010

I am pleased to report on progress in the financial affairs of EABIS. The end-of-year Balance Sheet and Profit and Loss statements for 2010 are presented to members at the General Assembly. Additionally, Management Accounts are reviewed by the Supervisory Board. Our Accountants have confirmed that these figures are fully consistent with the Statutory Accounts for 2010.

In terms of overall financial performance, the 2010 figures reflect a satisfactory outcome across all the organisations activities with a net surplus of over EUR 142,000 before exceptional items. This includes an operational surplus of EUR 5,680.

Operating income is heavily reliant on membership fees and retention of existing members is critical. A challenging recruitment target was set for 2010. I am pleased to report that total 2010 membership income of EUR 571,000 represents success in both objectives.

Of course, the majority of the overall organisational surplus is derived from activities on the corporate partners accounts where income exceeded expenditure committed in the course of 2010. However, the EABIS team is working with the individual corporate partners to further develop programmes that will see a substantial reduction in the accumulated reserves over time.

This will place further emphasis on tight control of the EABIS' resources. I can report that overall operational expenditure was marginally under budget in 2010

reflecting effective cost control at a time when the range and scope of EABIS' activity continues to expand. The 2010 Balance Sheet shows a small level by comparison with past years— some EUR 12,700 - of outstanding invoices due for payment at year end. Conversely, the Balance Sheet also shows EUR 164,000 of invoices, booked by our accountants in 2011, corresponding to EUR 146,000 paid in 2010, shown in the Balance Sheet under Realisable Assets, and fully incorporated in the 2010 Profit and Loss statement.

The Audit Committee has been concerned in recent years to see a reduction in the high level of Accounts Receivables at year end. To a large extent, this is an historic overhang from annual invoicing on the anniversary of members joining EABIS with a significant proportion of members invoiced in the final quarter of the financial year. The net Accounts Receivable at the end of 2010 is slightly down on the position at the end of 2009 after taking into account credit notes issued in 2011 against invoices issued in 2010 and represented in the 2010 Balance Sheet.

Further progress is needed and, on the recommendation of the Audit Committee, a timely staged member invoicing schedule was implemented in 2010 but not always matched by prompt payment. However, all but a small proportion of the Accounts Receivables due at the end of 2010 were paid in the first 2-3 months of 2011.

A prudent approach to outstanding Receivables has been adopted in line with recommendations of the Audit Committee. A provision of EUR 10,000 was included and utilised in the 2010 operating budget to cover fee income from member resignations during the year. The exceptional item shown in the Profit & Loss account was the write down of fees not paid in 2009 for which a EUR 10,000 provision was made in the 2009 budget. The Audit Committee continues to oversee progress in reducing the overall level of Accounts Receivable and the recovery of outstanding Receivables.

The main areas of operational expenditure, to be expected in a membership organisation, are HR and travel. Despite the increases in EABIS activities, average employee headcount fell slightly over the course of 2010. With anticipated growth in both workloads and travel generated from rising membership, the Audit Committee recommended to the Supervisory Board in June that a small working group of Board members be asked to review future EABIS resource needs and funding. The outcomes of the review are shortly to be presented to the Supervisory Board.

Dr Alexander A Holst
Chairman, Audit Committee
and EABIS Supervisory Board

EABIS Balance Sheet 2010

Assets		Balance at 31/12/2010
210000	Software	1,320.92Dt
210900	Depreciation on Software	1,320.92Ct
21	Intangibles Fixed Assets	<u>0.00Dt</u>
231000	Machinery / Air Conditioning	599.99Dt
239100	Depreciation on machinery	599.99Ct
23	Equipment & Installations	<u>0.00Dt</u>
		-
240000	Office	1,220.00Dt
240100	IT equipment	23,708.21Dt
	Depreciation on furniture and	
240900	IT material	13,724.31Ct
240909	Depreciation on Office	1,202.00Ct
24	Furniture & Material	<u>9,983.90Dt</u>
288000	Guarantee paid (Partena)	1,014.09Dt
28	Long-Term Loans	<u>1,014.09Dt</u>
2	FIXED ASSETS	10,997.99Dt
400000	Accounts receivable	581,588.98Dt
400410	Credit notes receivable	4,675.89Dt
402000	Payments	146,129.34Dt
404100	Invoices paid	44,963.54Dt
	Clients - disputed accounts	
407000	receivable	20,286.61Dt
411200	VAT receivable	24,207.83Dt
411300	VAT from originating country	1,901.33Dt
	Social Security provisions	
412000	receivable	2,408.54Dt
40/41	REALISABLE ASSETS	826,161.86Dt
550000	ING 310-1801678-86	42,207.44Dt
550100	ING 310-1801944-61	170,568.68Dt
550200	ING 310-1890040-81	0.01Dt
550400	ING 310-181801944-61 bis	175,025.26Dt
550500	ING 363-4599769-69	6,082.23Dt
5	AVAILABLE ASSETS	393,882.62Dt
490000	Bank charges receivable	126.83Dt
49	REGULARISATION	126.83Dt
	TOTAL ASSETS	1,231,170.30Dt

Liabilities		Balance at 31/12/2010
165100	Provisions - various	7,897.95Ct
16	PROVISIONS & OWN FUNDS	7,897.95Ct
440000	Suppliers	12,737.27Ct
444000	Invoice to receive	164,527.97Ct
444100	Credit notes to receive	105,800.00Ct
44	Commercial Debt	<u>283,065.24Ct</u>
453000	Employees' wages	4,084.42Ct
454000	Employees' Social Security	4,895.00Dt
456000	Holiday provision	21,558.45Ct
45	Tax and Social Security Debts	<u>30,537.87Ct</u>
44/45	DEBT (SHORT TERM)	313,603.11 Ct
70/68	Net Result for 2009	132,149.71 Ct
	Result from previous exercise	
790000	2009	777,519.53Ct
693000	OWN FUNDS	909,669.24Ct
	TOTAL LIABILITIES	1,231,170.30Ct

EABIS Profit & Loss Statement 2010

EABIS Profit & Loss Statement		Balance at 31/12/2010
700000	Membership Fees	571,290.00Ct
701000	Sponsorship Fees	375,203.53Ct
	Subvention EU	
702000	Commission	55,931.70Ct
70	Income from Activity	<u>1,002,425.23Ct</u>
740000	Insurance claim	4,585.56Ct
745100	Social Security refund	3,375.00Ct
	Precomte Professionnel exemption	619.85Ct
746000	Other expenses	
749000	re invoicing	49,892.89Ct
74	Other Income	<u>58,473.30Ct</u>
70/74	INCOME	1,060,898.53Ct
610000	Office rent	13,043.04Dt
610030	Rental flats - EasyLiving	1,770.00Dt
610200	Furniture rental	11,411.00Dt
	Materials and maintenance - fixed assets	10,133.21Dt
611000	Materials and maintenance - office	7,234.47Dt
612000	Utilities	722.30Dt
612100	Telephone, fax, postage	21,084.53Dt
612110	Internet	1,148.05Dt
612200	Documentation	4,541.06Dt
612300	Stationery & printing	17,084.64Dt
612500	Express Courier	1,463.62Dt
612600	Online Banking	599.67Dt
612700	Postal subscription	662.58Dt
613000	Redistribution to partners	100,000.00Dt
613010	Workshops / Seminars	40,260.60Dt
613020	Consulting fees	13,215.60Dt
613100	Fire insurance	281.68Dt
613140	General insurance	941.10Dt
613150	Travel insurance	60.13Dt
613200	Third party expenses	1,000.00Dt
613205	Meal vouchers	391.89Dt
613206		30,000.00Dt
613210	Lawyers & expert fees	6,660.00Dt
613211	Accountants fees	6,600.92Dt
613215	Social security fees	6,729.47Dt
613216	Diverse fees	3,063.42Dt
613217	Administrative fees	249.75Dt
613220	Membership fees	11,112.35Dt
613240	Legal case costs	375.00Dt
613250	Legal publications	59.73Dt
613260	IT / Website development	33,366.44Dt
613310	Travel / Accommodations	127,089.09Dt
613300	Personal transport	71.85Dt
613320	Public Transport / Taxi	3,939.37Dt
613330	Parking	112.64Dt
613610	Office meals	1,636.82Dt
	Notification, publication, Domain name	13,281.41Dt
614200	Photocopying	2,098.96Dt
614300	Seminars	38,387.99Dt
614500	Gifts	229.92Dt
614600	Business lunches	10,456.17Dt
614700	Documents	400.00Dt
615000	Subcontracting fees	223,263.70Dt

EABIS Profit & Loss Statement		Balance at 31/12/2010
61	General Expenditures	<u>765,549.29 Dt</u>
620200	Employee salaries	109,366.05 Dt
620205	Bonuses and supplements	4,988.33 Dt
620210	Double holiday bonus (pecule) Meal vouchers - employer	3,801.58 Dt
620800	contribution	2,769.61 Dt
621100	Social Security	21,590.04 Dt
623000	Personnel insurance	437.99 Ct
623200	Additional personnel costs	5,291.94 Dt
	Provision Holiday Pay 2009 - dotation	21,558.45 Dt
625000	Provision Holiday Pay 2008 - reprise	28,525.80 Ct
62	Personnel Costs	140,402.21 Dt

	Depreciation on intangible	
630200	fixed assets	6,584.90 Dt
630	Depreciation	<u>6,584.90 Dt</u>
640010	Office maintenance deduction	1,739.76 Dt
640200	Local and communal taxes	591.14 Dt
640900	TVA non deductible	2,510.09 Dt
643000	Taxes - various	2,983.72 Dt
640/8	Other operating expenses	<u>7,824.71 Dt</u>
650900	Credit card interest	1,731.86 Dt
650990	TVA Charges	607.11 Dt
657000	Bank fees	307.27 Dt
657010	Cash withdrawal fees	887.85 Dt
659000	Payment differentials	1.05 Dt
65	Financial Expenses	<u>3,535.14 Dt</u>
750010	Bank interest	139.92 Ct
750900	Exchange rate differentials	772.37 Ct
	Deduction / Third party differentials	554.60 Ct
757000		
758000	Difference in payments	3,701.53 Ct
75	Financial Income	<u>5,168.42 Ct</u>
	Net Profit Before Tax	<u>142,170.70 Dt</u>
663000	Exceptional charge	10,000.00 Dt
670010	Office furniture deduction	20.99 Dt
	Net Profit Balance	132,149.71 Ct

